

OPPORTUNITIES FOR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF PRODUCTION IN AGRICULTURE AND INCREASING THE EXPORT CAPACITY OF THE SECTOR

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Abstract. The article explores the possibilities of further development of production in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan and increasing the export potential of the sector.

Key words: agriculture, food products, market mechanisms, economic interests, farms, export.

Unlike other sectors belonging to the real sector of the economy, the organization of the agricultural sector in accordance with market requirements is relatively complicated. In the conditions of constantly changing market conditions, agricultural producers are faced with various socio-economic problems. In many ways, these problems are reflected in negative aspects such as lack of full understanding of market laws, insufficient development of market infrastructure, constant conflict of interests of producers operating in the agrarian sector, lack of accurate and sufficient information about the market situation.

There are real opportunities to further develop the production of food products in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan and to increase the export potential of the sector.

In particular, it should be noted that there are economic and organizational conditions that support the development of fruit and vegetable growing:

a) that the traditions and agrotechnical culture and skills of growing fruits and vegetables are preserved in households;

b) establishment of farms specializing in horticulture, fruit and vegetable and grape growing;

c) the fact that the working peasant and peasant farms are more oriented towards the cultivation of vegetables, fruits and grapes;

g) processes of agro-industry integration are observed in the network (many farms are starting to process their own products);

d) positive trends observed in the introduction of new technologies in the network;

e) volume of agricultural lending by commercial banks is rapidly increasing;

j) incentive tax system;

z) state financing of production infrastructure;

i) market infrastructure serving product sales;

k) availability of domestic demand for the product and demand outside the country;

l) that the product is competitive in terms of cost and consumer characteristics.

In 2020, 7566.6 thousand tons of grain, 10459.5 thousand tons of vegetables, 2134.4 thousand tons of processed products, 3143.5 thousand tons of potatoes, 2864.0 thousand tons of fruit, 1639.2 thousand tons of grapes were produced in Uzbekistan. According to official data, 290 kilograms of vegetables, 140 kilograms of fruits, 75 kilograms of potatoes, 40 kilograms of meat and meat products, 30 kilograms of sugar, 210 eggs, 270 liters of milk and dairy products, 25 kilograms of vegetable oil are consumed per year. According to the recommendations of the World Health Organization, the norm of fruit and vegetable consumption for an adult is 400 grams per day. Population consumption in Uzbekistan is five times higher

than this norm, and in addition to domestic consumption, large volumes of export can be launched.

The opportunities for export of food products produced in agriculture remain insufficiently exploited. Export of fruits and vegetables in 2020 is 1008.6 mln. amounted to dollars (83.5% of the export in 2019, and in 2018, the export volume was 1 million tons and 1 billion dollars). That is why the government is taking measures to increase this indicator [1].

In recent years, significant positive changes have been taking place in the introduction of market mechanisms to the agricultural sector. The use of the cluster system serves to ensure the priority of economic interests in the activities of economic entities in the production and financial activities, and the interference of state institutions in their activities is reduced. As a result, along with the development of traditional branches of agriculture, new ones are emerging: modern greenhouses, fisheries, beekeeping, poultry, saffron, hot pepper, garlic and onion cultivation, planting of vegetable crops as a secondary (repeat) crop in the fall, development of real estate in the direction of commercialization and others [2].

The creation and efficient operation of specialized farms, the orientation of family farms to horticulture, vegetable and viticulture, and the acceleration of the processes of agro-industry integration (farmers start processing their own products) should have a serious socio-economic effect. Business entities in the network have a real inclination to innovation. This is more evident due to the factors of technological updates, expanding financial opportunities, reducing the tax burden on private business. Other aspects can also be noted. The production infrastructure is mainly financed by the state.

Implementation of the concept of development of Uzbekistan's agriculture until 2030 is extremely important in order to expand fruit and vegetable cultivation and strengthen the export potential of the sector. In it, the necessary measures for the consistent implementation of market relations in the agricultural sector were defined:

- agricultural producers are given freedom in choosing crop types and sales markets;
- From 2020, the transition to the formation of prices for all crops through the market;
- real strengthening of land use rights;
- increase of land productivity and protection of the rights of plant originators;
- export of agricultural products is 2.3 bln. 20 billion dollars in 2030 . deliver up to dollars ;
- rational management of water resources (transition to market principles), water saving [3].

Within the framework of this concept, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a decision on January 11, 2021 "On measures to develop fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture in Kosonsoy, Chortoq and Yangigurgan districts of Namangan region." In the decision, urgent tasks in the development of the sector and measures to ensure their fulfillment were defined. According to the President's decision, the land tax paid by farms and other agricultural organizations that grow certified seeds of vegetable, leguminous and oil crops, as well as fruit trees and vine seedlings in the specified districts will be reduced by 50% for a period of three years. Also, the interest rate on loans allocated in national currency to finance the costs of purchasing seeds and seedlings of clusters and cooperatives, which exceeds the main rate of the Central Bank, but not more than 10 percentage points, as well as up to 30% of the interest rate on loans allocated in foreign currency, but not more than 3 percentage points at least part of it is covered by the funds of the State Fund for the Support of Entrepreneurial Activities. In addition, from 2023, 300,000 tons of potatoes, 6,000 tons of legumes, and 11,000 tons of oilseeds will be produced every year. 26 million for these purposes. dollars are directed.

Special attention is paid to improving logistics for further development of exports. Of course, in order to triple the volumes of processing and export, the full commissioning and operation of processing plants, cold storage warehouses and

logistics centers will be ensured during 2021-2022. In 2022, 200,000 tons of storage capacity should be put into operation.

2.5 billion will be allocated to agriculture in 2018-2022. USD 1.7 billion foreign loans were attracted. 4,000 projects were implemented due to the appropriation of dollars. In 2022, 80,000 hectares of land will be allocated to the population due to the reduction of cotton and grain cultivation areas, and food and animal feed crops will be planted in these areas. Another 100,000 hectares will be allocated in 2023. The system of economic relations in grain cultivation is being radically changed. On May 28, 2022, the Presidential Decree "On additional measures to introduce the market principle in the cultivation and sale of grain" was adopted. The transfer of settlements with producers to free market prices ensured a 2-fold increase in their income.

The problems of fruit and vegetable development can be described as follows. It is necessary to bring the material and technical support of the network to the level of modern requirements:

- a) lack of specialized equipment;
- b) that the level of use of advanced agricultural technology is low;
- c) failure to satisfy the demand for chemicals and mineral fertilizers and their prices, monopolization of sales;
- g) sorting and storage facilities are insufficient and uneconomical.

Problems in financial support of fruit and vegetable farming:

a) the majority of fruit and grape growing farms do not have authorized capital, which means that their financial support is practically not guaranteed by the owners;

b) proceeds from the sale of products in most cases bypass the banking system, in turn, banks do not provide quality service to enterprises operating in the network, do not help them with their calculations, resources are allocated for them in the last place during the lending process, and they approach cash supply in the same way;

c) financial planning is not established in farms, the financial knowledge of

farm managers is not up to the level of requirements, the non-existence of accounting leads to the non-existence of financial control [4].

There are also problems with selling a network product:

a) domestic wholesale buyers of products and large processors force producers to sell their products at unreasonably low prices, which is caused by the insufficient number of wholesale sales channels. It is necessary to waive the obligation to conclude sales contracts in advance;

b) the modern infrastructure of the wholesale sale of fruit, vegetables and grape products is insufficient, the share of the procurement system in the wholesale trade is very low, the offered prices do not completely satisfy the producers;

c) difficulties in long-distance delivery of products remain, the fact that the capacity of the long-term product storage system is very small increases the seasonal nature of sales and makes it difficult to adjust supply to demand;

g) in the actual procedure of exporting fruits, vegetables and grapes, the exporter is forced to perform many economically unnecessary actions when exporting the product. There is no competition among buyers in the wholesale market of export purchases, because their scope is limited, this sector of the market is monopolized, and producers suffer from it [5].

In our opinion, further development of fruit and vegetable production and increase of export potential it is necessary to encourage voluntary mergers of horticultural farms and peasant farms into large cooperatives by providing financial incentives to large producers in the network, to introduce a minimum amount of authorized capital for each category of farms, to allow farms to receive targeted financial support and loans from processing enterprises and wholesale buyers.

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